

Human Cytomegalovirus is the Cause of Glioblastoma Multiforme

Ilija Barukčić¹

¹ Internist, Horandstrasse, DE-26441 Jever, Germany

Correspondence: Ilija Barukčić, Horandstrasse, DE-26441 Jever, Germany. Tel: 0049-(0)4466-333. E-mail: Barukcic@t-online.de

Received: August 9, 2018; Accepted: September 11, 2018; Published: September 19, 2018

Abstract

Objective: The relationship between Human cytomegalovirus (HCMV) and glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) is investigated.

Methods: A systematic review and re-analysis of some impressive key studies was conducted aimed to answer the following question. Is there a cause-effect relationship between HCMV and GBM? The method of the *conditio sine qua non* relationship was used to proof the hypothesis whether the presence of HCMV guarantees the presence of GBM. In other words, *without HCMV no GBM*. The mathematical formula of the causal relationship k was used to proof the hypothesis, whether there is a cause-effect relationship between HCMV and GBM. Significance was indicated by a p -value of less than 0.05.

Results: The studies analysed were able to provide strict evidence that HCMV is a necessary condition (a *conditio sine qua non*) of GBM. Furthermore, the cause-effect relationship between HCMV and GBM ($k \sim + 0.8608$, p value < 0.0001) was highly significant.

Conclusion: Without a human cytomegalovirus infection no glioblastoma multiforme. Human cytomegalovirus is the cause of glioblastoma multiforme.

Keywords: Cytomegalovirus, Glioblastoma multiforme, Causal relationship

1. Introduction

Glioblastoma (Bailey & Cushing, 1926) multiforme (GBM) is a highly lethal (Zhu et al., 2002), non-curable grade IV diffuse astrocytoma (brain tumour) which is affecting children and adults to such an extent that to date the majority of affected patients are dying from their disease by 2,5 years following diagnosis (Smoll et al., 2013). Glioblastoma multiforme consist primarily of neoplastic astrocytes but includes also other non-neoplastic cell types (Yuan et al., 2004) like neural stem cells, macrophages et cetera. The commonly used World Health Organization (WHO) classification distinguishes different types of glioblastoma multiforme (Louis et al., 2007) due to the presumed cell of origin. In general, glioblastoma multiforme may first appear as a grade 4 glioblastoma (GBM) and is called primary GBM while secondary glioblastoma multiforme develops from a lower grade astrocytoma. The Cancer Genome Atlas (Verhaak et al., 2010) researchers classified four subtypes of GBM as Proneural, Neural, Classical, and Mesenchymal subtypes. In point of fact, even if Glioblastoma multiforme progresses rapidly and is fatal within a very short time despite current therapies, to date the aetiology of glioblastoma multiforme is completely unknown. Among several risk factors supposed to be involved in glioblastoma including exposure to electrical or magnetic fields or ionizing radiation (Ohgaki, 2009) human cytomegalovirus too has been proposed as a contributing agent of glioblastoma multiforme. To our knowledge, HCMV as a member of the Betaherpesvirinae subfamily (Landolfo et al., 2003) is containing a linear double-stranded DNA of 230 kb surrounded by a proteinaceous tegument, which itself is enclosed by a loosely applied lipid bilayer and contains more than 60 virus-encoded proteins and about 70 host-proteins. The proteins produced by the HCMV can be detected (Landolfo et al., 2003) in various human cellular compartments i.e. by means of immunohistochemistry (IHC). A primary human cytomegalovirus infection leads to a life-long viral persistence. In the latent phase of a HCMV infection HCMV virions are not produced and patients are more or less clinically without symptoms (Priel et al., 2015) but HCMV itself can be present in the monocytes. The seroprevalence of HCMV in the general human population ranges between 50 to 100% (Gandhi & Khanna, 2004; Ludwig & Hengel, 2009; Yi et al., 2013; Najafi et al., 2016). Even a foetus itself is not protected against a vertical transmission. Thus far, HCMV represents the major infectious cause of serious birth defects or developmental disabilities. During maternal primary infection, and to a lesser extent during recurrent infection, human

cytomegalovirus can translocate the placental barrier and can cause infection of the developing foetus too. Human cytomegalovirus is occurring in 0.5-2% of pregnancies in Europe and the United States (Kenneson et al., 2007; Wang et al., 2011) and neonatal infections (Fowler et al., 2018) caused by human cytomegalovirus have been reported too. In particular, many breast milk-acquired infections in premature infants are asymptomatic. Several studies demonstrated the presence of human cytomegalovirus in glioblastoma tissues suggesting that HCMV may participate in tumour pathogenesis. But the relationship between GBM and HCMV is controversial because many other studies were unable to detect HCMV in Glioblastoma multiforme tissues.

2. Material and methods

2.1 Material

2.1.1 Search Strategy

To answer the questions addressed in this paper, the electronic database PubMed was searched for appropriate studies conducted in any country which investigated the relationship between human cytomegalovirus and glioblastoma multiforme i. e. sero-epidemiologically or by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) et cetera. The search in PubMed was performed while using some medical key words like "case control study" and "cytomegalovirus" and "glioblastoma multiforme" et cetera. The articles found were saved as a *.txt file while using the support of PubMed. The created *.txt file was converted into a *.pdf file. The abstracts were studied within the *.pdf file. Those articles were considered for a re-view which provided access to data without any data access barrier. Additionally the reference list of identified articles was used as a potential source of articles appropriate for this study.

2.1.2. The 2x2 Table

The meaning of the abbreviations a_t , b_t , c_t , d_t , N_t of the data table used are explained by a 2 by 2-table **Table 1**.

Table 1. The sample space of a contingency table.

		Conditioned B_t		Total
		(Outcome)		
		Yes = +1	Not = +0	
Condition A_t (risk factor)	Yes =+1	a_t	b_t	A_t
	Not = +0	c_t	d_t	\underline{A}_t
	Total	B_t	\underline{B}_t	N_t

In general it is $(a_t+b_t) = A_t$, $(c_t+d_t) = \underline{A}_t$, $(a_t+c_t) = B_t$, $(b_t+d_t) = \underline{B}_t$ and $a_t+b_t+c_t+d_t=N_t$. Equally, it is $B_t+\underline{B}_t = A_t + \underline{A}_t = N_t$. In this context, it is $p(a_t)=p(A_t \cap B_t)$, $p(A_t) = p(a_t)+p(b_t)$ or $p(A_t) = p(A_t \cap B_t)+ p(b_t) =p(A_t \cap B_t)+p(A_t \cap \underline{B}_t)$ while $p(A_t)$ is not defined as $p(a_t)$. In the same context, it is $p(B_t) = p(a_t)+p(c_t) = p(A_t \cap B_t) +p(c_t)$ and equally in the same respect $p(\underline{B}_t) = 1- p(B_t) =p(b_t)+p(d_t)$. Furthermore, the joint probability of A_t and B_t is denoted in general by $p(A_t \cap B_t)$. Thus far, it is $p(A_t \cap B_t) = p(A_t) - p(b_t) = p(B_t) - p(c_t)$ or in other words it follows clearly that $p(B_t) + p(b_t) - p(c_t) = p(A_t)$. Thus far, define $\Lambda = p(b_t) - p(c_t)$, Einstein's term Λ under conditions of probability theory and we obtain $p(B_t) + \Lambda = p(A_t)$. In general, it is $p(a_t)+p(c_t)+p(b_t)+p(d_t) = 1$.

2.1.3 The Studies not Analyzed

The studies of Baumgarten et al. (2014), Holdhoff et al. (2017) and Wrensch et al. (2005) which investigated the relationship between HCMV serostatus and glioblastoma patients were not considered for a review. The study of Yamashita et al. (2014) did not detect HCMV DNA in any of the glioblastoma cases by real-time quantitative PCR (QPCR). Still, while using immunoblotting and immunohistochemistry tissue samples were partly positive according to Yamashita et al. (2014). Thus, it remains unclear the extent to which the methods used by Yamashita et al. (2014) were able to detect the entire HCMV genome when present. Yang et al. (2017) investigated the presence of HCMV genes in human glioblastoma multiforme cases by quantitative PCR using inappropriate HCMV *UL73*. The data were not re-analyzed.

2.1.4 The Studies Used to Analyze the Conditio Sine Qua non Relationship between HCMV and GBM

The studies used to analyze the conditio sine qua non relationship between HCMV and GBM are viewed by the **Table 2**.

Table 2. *Without human cytomegalovirus infection no glioblastoma multiforme.*

Study Id	Year	Country	N	a _t	b _t	c _t	d _t	p(SINE)	X ² (Sine)	k	X ² (k)	p val (k)
Cobbs et al.	2002	USA	45	22	0	0	23	1	0.0114	1.0000	45.0000	< 0.0001
Mitchell et al.	2008	USA	90	42	0	3	45	0.9666667	0.1389	0.9354	78.7500	< 0.0001
Scheurer et al.	2008	USA	42	21	0	0	21	1	0.0119	1.0000	42.0000	< 0.0001
Dziurzynski et al.	2011	USA	10	5	0	0	5	1	Rule of 3	1.0000	-	-
Ranganathan et al.	2012	USA	90	73	2	2	13	0.9777778	0.0300	0.8400	63.5040	< 0.0001
Rahbar et al.	2012	Sweden	160	79	0	1	80	0.99375	0.0031	0.9876	156.0494	< 0.0001
Libard et al.	2014	Sweden	86	65	0	7	14	0.9186047	0.5868	0.7758	51.7593	< 0.0001
Ding et al.	2014	China	73	51	0	16	6	0.7808219	3.5858	0.4556	15.1547	0.0001
Wakefield et al.	2015	USA	48	14	0	10	24	0.7916667	3.7604	0.6417	19.7647	< 0.0001
Xing et al.	2016	China	51	40	0	3	8	0.9411765	0.1453	0.8225	34.5032	< 0.0001
Stangherlin et al.	2016	Brazil	23	9	1	1	12	0.9565217	0.0250	0.8231	-	-
Slinger et al.	2010	Netherlands	42	20	12*	1	9*	0.9761905	0.0119	-	-	-
Lucas et al.	2011	USA	90	25	25*	20	20*	0.7777778	8.4500	-	-	-
Bhattacharjee et al.	2012	USA	34	16	10*	1	7*	0.9705882	0.0147	-	-	-
Rahbar et al.	2013	Sweden	150	74	40*	1	35*	0.9933333	0.0033	-	-	-
dos Santos et al.	2014	Brazil	44	21	12*	1	10*	0.9772727	0.0114	-	-	-
Total			1078	577	102	67	332	0.9378479	16.19			
Alpha =						0.05						
Degrees of freedom (d. f.) =						15						
X ² Critical (SINE) =						24.996						
X ² Calculated (SINE) =						16.19						

***fictive values (due to a missing control group)**

The data as presented by Ranganathan et al. (2012) clearly demonstrated that HCMV genomes are associated with GBM tumors. Even if presentation and illustration of the data of the study of Ranganathan et al. (2012) was difficult to analyze, it was possible to use the data of HCMV UL69. Several of the studies presented above are missing an own control group. Especially the studies of dos Santos et al. (2014), Slinger et al. (2010), Bhattacharjee et al. (2012), Lucas et al. (2011), Holdhoff et al. (2017), Baumgarten et al. (2014) did not provide a suitable control group. This fact has no mathematical influence on the calculation of the chi square value of the necessary condition. Still, we calculated a fictive control group due to the fact that the seroprevalence of HCMV in the general human population ranges between 50 to 100% (Gandhi & Khanna, 2004; Ludwig & Hengel, 2009; Yi et al., 2013; Najafi et al., 2016).

2.1.5 The studies Used to Analyze the Necessary and Sufficient Condition Relationship and the Causal Relationship Between HCMV and GBM

Table 3. The necessary and sufficient condition relationship and the causal relationship between HCVm and GBM

Study Id	Year	Country	N	a _t	b _t	c _t	d _t	p(IMP^SINE)	X ² (IMP^SINE)	k	X ² (k)	p val (k)
Cobbs et al.	2002	USA	45	22	0	0	23	1	0.0227	1	45.00	< 0.0001
Mitchell et al.	2008	USA	90	42	0	3	45	0.96666667	0.1448	0.935	78.75	< 0.0001
Scheurer et al.	2008	USA	42	21	0	0	21	1	0.0238	1	42.00	< 0.0001
Dziurzynski et al.	2011	USA	10	5	0	0	5	1	Rule of 3	1	10.00	0.0016
Ranganathan et al.	2012	USA	90	73	2	2	13	0.95555556	0.0600	0.84	63.50	< 0.0001
Rahbar et al.	2012	Sweden	160	79	0	1	80	0.99375	0.0063	0.9875	156.05	< 0.0001
Libard et al.	2014	Sweden	86	65	0	7	14	0.918604651	0.5907	0.7757	51.76	< 0.0001
Ding et al.	2014	China	73	51	0	16	6	0.780821918	3.5907	0.4556	15.15	0.0001
Wakefield et al.	2015	USA	48	14	0	10	24	0.791666667	3.7783	0.6416	19.76	< 0.0001
Xing et al.	2016	China	51	40	0	3	8	0.941176471	0.1516	0.8225	34.50	< 0.0001
Stangherlin et al.	2016	Brazil	23	9	1	1	12	0.913043478	Rule of 3	0.8230	15.58	0.0001
Total			718	421	3	43	251	0.935933148	8.3689	0.8608	532.06	
Alpha =						0.05			Alpha = 0.05			
Degrees of freedom (d. f.) =						9			Degrees of freedom (d. f.) = 11			
X ² Critical (SINE^IMP) =						16.91			X ² Critical (k) = 19.6751			
X ² Calculated (SINE^IMP) =						8.368			X ² Calculated (k) = 532.06			
										p value (k) < 0.0001		

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Statistical Analysis

All statistical analyses (Barukčć. 1989; Barukčć. 2017a; Barukčć. 2017b; Barukčć. 2017c; Barukčć. 2018a; Barukčć. 2018b; Barukčć. 2018c) were performed with Microsoft Excel version 14.0.7166.5000 (32-Bit) Software (Microsoft GmbH. Munich. Germany). The level of significance was set to 0.05. The probabilities of the contingency table are viewed by the following table (Table 4).

Table 4. The probabilities of a contingency table

		Conditioned		
		B _t		
Condition A _t		Yes = +1	No = +0	Total
		Yes = +1	$p(a_t) = p(A_t \cap B_t)$	$p(b_t)$
No = +0	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$	
Total	$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	1	

2.2.2 Independence

In the case of independence of A_t and B_t it is generally valid that

$$p(A_t \cap B_t) \equiv p(A_t) \times p(B_t) \tag{1}$$

2.2.3 Exclusion (A_t Excludes B_t and Vice Versa Relationship)

The mathematical formula of the *exclusion* relationship (A_t excludes B_t and vice versa) of a population was defined (Barukčć, 2016a; Barukčć, 2017a; Barukčć, 2017b; Barukčć, 2017c; Barukčć, 2018a; Barukčć, 2018b; Barukčć, 2018c) as

$$p(A_t | B_t) \equiv \frac{b_t + c_t + d_t}{N_t} \equiv 1 - p(a_t) \equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \equiv p(c_t) + (1 - p(B_t)) \equiv p(b_t) + (1 - p(A_t)) \equiv +1 \tag{2}$$

and used to proof the hypothesis: A_t *excludes* B_t and vice versa.

2.2.4 Necessary Condition (Conditio Sine Qua Non)

The mathematical formula of the *necessary* condition relationship (conditio sine qua non) of a population was defined (Barukčć, 2016a; Barukčć, 2017a; Barukčć, 2017b; Barukčć, 2017c; Barukčć, 2018a; Barukčć, 2018b; Barukčć, 2018c) as

$$p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv \frac{a_t + b_t + d_t}{N_t} \equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t) \equiv p(a_t) + (1 - p(B_t)) \equiv +1 \tag{3}$$

and used to proof the hypothesis: *without* A_t *no* B_t .

2.2.5. Sufficient Condition (Conditio per Quam)

The mathematical formula of the *sufficient* condition relationship (conditio per quam) of a population was defined (Barukčć, 2016a; Barukčć, 2017a; Barukčć, 2017b; Barukčć, 2017c; Barukčć, 2018a; Barukčć, 2018b; Barukčć, 2018c) as

$$p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) \equiv \frac{a_t + c_t + d_t}{N_t} \equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \equiv p(d_t) + p(B_t) \equiv +1 \tag{4}$$

and used to proof the hypothesis: *if* A_t *then* B_t .

2.2.6 The X² Goodness of Fit Test of a Necessary Condition

Under conditions where the chi-square goodness of fit test (Pearson, 1900) cannot be used it is possible to use an approximate and conservative (one sided) confidence interval known as *the rule of three* (Rumke, 1975; Hanley et

al., 1983; Louis, 1981; Jovanovic et al., 1997). According to the definition of the *conditio sine qua non* relationship it is

$$p(A_t \cap B_t) + (1 - p(B_t)) \equiv +1 \quad (5)$$

or

$$p(A_t \cap B_t) + 1 - p(B_t) \equiv +1 \quad (6)$$

Rearranging this equation, we obtain the essential foundation of the *conditio sine qua non* relationship as

$$p(A_t \cap B_t) = p(B_t) \quad (7)$$

and equally our starting point of the derivation of chi-square value of the *conditio sine qua non* relationship. Multiplying equation before by the population or sample/population size N. it is

$$N \times p(A_t \cap B_t) \equiv N \times p(B_t) \quad (8)$$

or

$$N \times p(A_t \cap B_t) - N \times p(B_t) = 0 \quad (9)$$

The square operation yields

$$(N \times p(A_t \cap B_t) - N \times p(B_t)) \times (N \times p(A_t \cap B_t) - N \times p(B_t)) = 0 \times 0 \quad (10)$$

Dividing by $N \times p(B_t)$ we obtain

$$\frac{(N \times p(A_t \cap B_t) - N \times p(B_t))^2}{N \times p(B_t)} = 0 \quad (11)$$

which is equivalent with

$$\frac{(a_t - (B_t))^2}{(B_t)} = \frac{(a_t - (a_t + c_t))^2}{(B_t)} = \frac{(c_t)^2}{(B_t)} = 0 \quad (12)$$

Adding $((b_t + d_t) - (B_t))^2 / B_t = ((b_t + d_t) - (b_t + d_t))^2 / B_t = 0$ yields

$$\frac{(c_t)^2}{(B_t)} + 0 = 0 + 0 \quad (13)$$

Using *the continuity correction* (Yates, 1934), the chi-square value of a *conditio sine qua non* distribution before changes to

$$\chi^2 (\text{SINE}) \equiv \frac{\left(c_t - \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) \right)^2}{(B_t)} + 0 = 0 \quad (14)$$

The use of the continuity correction should follow the rules of statistics as established and valid today. This definition of the X^2 distribution of a *conditio sine qua non* distribution (degrees of freedom = 2-1=1) is more precise than already published formulas. In this context, it is not necessary to improve the definition of the X^2 distribution of a *conditio per quam* distribution as already published. The significance of a causal relationship k which is $k > 0$ is supported by a significant *conditio sine qua non* relationship; otherwise the result of a study should be treated with cautious.

2.2.7 The X² Goodness of Fit Test of the Exclusion Relationship

According to the definition of the exclusion relationship (Barukčić, 2016a; Barukčić, 2017a; Barukčić, 2017b; Barukčić, 2017c; Barukčić, 2018a; Barukčić, 2018b; Barukčić, 2018c) it is

$$p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \equiv +1 \tag{15}$$

Rearranging this equation, we obtain

$$p(b_t) = 1 - p(c_t) - p(d_t) = 1 - (p(c_t) + p(d_t)) \equiv 1 - p(\underline{A}_t) = p(A_t) \tag{16}$$

and

$$p(c_t) = 1 - p(b_t) - p(d_t) \equiv 1 - (p(b_t) + p(d_t)) = 1 - p(\underline{B}_t) = p(B_t) \tag{17}$$

The chi square goodness of fit test of the exclusion relationship can be derived as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{N \times p(b_t)}{(N \times p(b_t) - N \times p(A_t)) \times (N \times p(b_t) - N \times p(A_t))} &= \frac{N \times p(A_t)}{0} \\ &= 0 \times 0 \\ \frac{(N \times p(b_t) - N \times p(A_t))^2}{N \times p(A_t)} &= \frac{0}{N \times p(A_t)} = 0 \\ \chi^2(b_t) = \frac{(N \times p(b_t) - N \times p(A_t))^2}{N \times p(A_t)} = \frac{(b_t - (a_t + b_t))^2}{A_t} = \frac{(-a_t)^2}{A_t} &= 0 \\ \chi^2(b_t) = \frac{(-a_t - 0,5)^2}{A_t} &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

and as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{N \times p(c_t)}{(N \times p(c_t) - N \times p(B_t)) \times (N \times p(c_t) - N \times p(B_t))} &= \frac{N \times p(B_t)}{0} \\ &= 0 \times 0 \\ \frac{(N \times p(c_t) - N \times p(B_t))^2}{N \times p(B_t)} &= \frac{0}{N \times p(B_t)} = 0 \\ \chi^2(c_t) = \frac{(N \times p(c_t) - N \times p(B_t))^2}{N \times p(B_t)} = \frac{(c_t - (a_t + c_t))^2}{B_t} = \frac{(-a_t)^2}{B_t} &= 0 \\ \chi^2(c_t) = \frac{(-a_t - 0,5)^2}{B_t} &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

The chi square value with degree of freedom 2-1=1 of the exclusion relationship with a *continuity correction* (Yates, 1934) can be calculated as

$$\chi^2(EXCL) = \frac{(-a_t - 0,5)^2}{A_t} + \frac{(-a_t - 0,5)^2}{B_t} \tag{20}$$

A significant causal relationship k which is $k < 0$ is supported by an exclusion relationship otherwise the results of a study can be interpreted with some cautious. It would be a mistake not to consider all aspects of the relationship between cause and effect. Finally, it should be noted that the fundamental concepts of necessary and sufficient conditions is one of the handy tools which can help us to proof causal claims too.

2.2.8 The Mathematical Formula of the Causal Relationship k

The mathematical formula of the causal relationship k (Barukć, 2016a; Barukć, 2017a; Barukć, 2017b; Barukć, 2017c; Barukć, 2018a; Barukć, 2018b; Barukć, 2018c; Barukć, 2018d; Barukć, 2018e; Barukć, 2018f; Barukć, 2018g) is defined *at every single event, at every single Bernoulli trial t* , as

$$k(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{(p(A_t \cap B_t) - (p(A_t) \times p(B_t)))}{\sqrt{(p(A_t) \times p(\underline{A}_t)) \times (p(B_t) \times p(\underline{B}_t))}} \tag{21}$$

where A_t denotes the cause and B_t denotes the effect. The chi-square distribution can be applied to determine the significance of causal relationship k . Pearson’s concept of correlation (Pearson, 1896) is not identical with causation, causation (Heisenberg, 1927; Einstein & Podolsky & Rosen, 1935; Bohr, 1937; Einstein, 1948) is not identical with correlation. In particular, the relationship between correlation and causation has already been discussed in many publications (Wright, 1921; Sober, 2001). Thus far, repeating itself over and over again on this topic is only a waste of time and will not contribute anything new to further scientific progress.

2.2.9 The 95% Confidence Interval of the Causal Relationship k

A confidence interval (CI) of the causal relationship k calculated from the statistics of the observed data can help to estimate the true value of an unknown population parameter with a certain probability. Let the sample mean S be

$$S = \overline{k(A_t, B_t)} = \frac{k(A_1, B_1) + k(A_2, B_2) + \dots + k(A_n, B_n)}{n} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n k(A_t, B_t)}{n} \tag{22}$$

Since $k(A_t, B_t)$ is Bernoulli(p) distributed with $E(k(A_t, B_t)) = (1 \times p(k(A_t, B_t))) + (0 \times (1 - p(k(A_t, B_t)))) = p(k(A_t, B_t))$ where $E(k(A_t, B_t))$ denotes the expected value of $k(A_t, B_t)$ it is

$$E(S) = p(k(A_t, B_t)) \text{ and } \sigma(S)^2 = \frac{p(k(A_t, B_t)) \times (1 - p(k(A_t, B_t)))}{n} \tag{23}$$

where $\sigma(S)^2$ denotes the variance of the sampling distribution of $p(k(A_t, B_t))$. When the sample size is not too small, the central limit theorem based normal approximation can be used to estimate the confidence interval (CI) as

$$p(k(A_t, B_t)) \pm \left(Z \times \sqrt{\frac{p(k(A_t, B_t)) \times (1 - p(k(A_t, B_t)))}{n}} \right) = p(k(A_t, B_t)) \pm \left(\sqrt{\frac{Z^2}{n} \times p(k(A_t, B_t)) \times (1 - p(k(A_t, B_t)))} \right) \tag{24}$$

where $p(k(A_t, B_t))$ denotes the proportion of successes in a Bernoulli trial process and Z is the $(1 - (\alpha/2))$ quantile of a standard normal distribution. For a 95% confidence level $Z \sim 1.96$, For an unknown standard deviation the Student's t distribution t can be used as the critical value. Still, it is known that $\sigma(S)^2$ has the maximum value $(1/(4 \times n))$ when $p=1/2$ and we have

$$p(k(A_t, B_t)) \pm \left(\sqrt{\frac{Z^2}{4 \times n}} \right) \Leftrightarrow p(k(A_t, B_t)) \pm \left(\sqrt{\frac{1.96^2}{4 \times n}} \right) \approx p(k(A_t, B_t)) \pm \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{2 \times n}} \right) \tag{25}$$

The proposed approximation is of use even under circumstances where $p(\dots) = 0.9999 \dots 999 \sim p=1$. In this context, we obtain the critical value $p_{critical}$ approximately as $p_{critical} = 1 - (1/(2n))^{1/2}$. In particular, the concept of Chebyshev’s inequality (Tchébychef, 1867) is profound because the same inequality is true for every distribution even if the distribution isn’t normal. Thus far, Chebyshev’s inequality allows calculating the 95% confidence of the causal relationship k and so by the Chebyshev inequality it is

$$p\left\{p(k(A_t, B_t)) - c \times \sqrt[2]{\sigma(S)^2} < S < p(k(A_t, B_t)) + c \times \sqrt[2]{\sigma(S)^2}\right\} \geq 1 - \frac{1}{c^2} \tag{26}$$

were the right side has the value 0.95 when $c = (20)^{1/2}$. This is the case since $(1 - (1/c^2)) = 0.95$ or $0.05 = (1/c^2)$ or $c^2 = (1/0.05)$ or $c^2 = (100/5)$ or $c^2 = 20$ or $c = (20)^{1/2}$. Thus far, if S does lie in the interval

$$\left\{p(k(A_t, B_t)) - \sqrt[2]{20 \times \sigma(S)^2}, p(k(A_t, B_t)) + \sqrt[2]{20 \times \sigma(S)^2}\right\} \tag{27}$$

then $p(k(A_t, B_t))$ itself must be in the interval

$$\left\{S - \sqrt[2]{20 \times \sigma(S)^2}, S + \sqrt[2]{20 \times \sigma(S)^2}\right\} \tag{28}$$

which is equally the 95% confidence interval for an unknown parameter $p(k(A_t, B_t))$. Again, $\sigma(S)^2$ has the maximum value $(1/(4 \times n))$ when $p = 1/2$, so we have

$$\left\{S - \sqrt[2]{\frac{20 \times 1}{4 \times n}}, S + \sqrt[2]{\frac{20 \times 1}{4 \times n}}\right\} \tag{29}$$

or the 95% interval for the causal relationship k as

$$\left\{k(A_t, B_t) - \sqrt[2]{\frac{5}{n}}, k(A_t, B_t) + \sqrt[2]{\frac{5}{n}}\right\} \tag{30}$$

2.2.10 Odds Ratio

The odds ratio (OR) is given (Cornfield, 1951; Edwards, 1963; Mosteller, 1968) by

$$OR(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{a_t / b_t}{c_t / d_t} = \frac{a_t \times d_t}{c_t \times b_t} \tag{31}$$

Under conditions were $c_t = 0$ we have a *conditio sine qua non* relationship while the odds ratio collapses. Under conditions were $b_t = 0$ we have a *conditio per quam* relationship but the odds ratio collapses again, since to date it is not generally accepted (Barukčić & Barukčić, 2016b; Barukčić, 2018d) to divide by zero. To avoid confusion on this issue, 0.5 is added to the cells a, b, c, d (Pagano & Gauvreau, 2018), if zero causes some problems with the calculation of the odds ratio or its standard error which is often very misleading. In point of fact, the odds ratio (OR) is nothing more but *Yule's coefficient of association Q* (Yule, 1900) re-written (Warrens, 2008) in a non-normalized form and given by

$$Q(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{OR(A_t, B_t) - 1}{OR(A_t, B_t) + 1} = \frac{\frac{(a_t \times d_t)}{(b_t \times c_t)} - 1}{\frac{(a_t \times d_t)}{(b_t \times c_t)} + 1} = \frac{(a_t \times d_t) - (b_t \times c_t)}{(a_t \times d_t) + (b_t \times c_t)} = \frac{(a_t \times d_t) - (b_t \times c_t)}{(a_t \times d_t) - (b_t \times c_t)} \tag{32}$$

If $Q = 0$ then there is no association. Yule's coefficient of association, Q, and thus far Odds ratio itself, has been severely criticized by Karl Pearson (1857–1925), the long-time and rarely challenged leader of statistical science and by Heron (Pearson & Heron, 1913). The standard error and 95% confidence interval of the odds ratio (OR) can be calculated according to Altman (Altman, 1991). The standard error of the log odds ratio is given by

$$SE(\ln(OR(A_t, B_t))) \equiv \sqrt{\frac{1}{a_t} + \frac{1}{b_t} + \frac{1}{c_t} + \frac{1}{d_t}} \tag{33}$$

where *ln* denotes the logarithmus naturalis. The 95% confidence interval of the odds ratio is given by

$$95\% \text{ CI} = \exp\left(\ln(\text{OR}(A_i, B_i)) - (1.96 \times \text{SE}(\ln(\text{OR}(A_i, B_i))))\right) \text{ to } \exp\left(\ln(\text{OR}(A_i, B_i)) + (1.96 \times \text{SE}(\ln(\text{OR}(A_i, B_i))))\right) \quad (34)$$

2.2.11 The Chi Square Distribution

The following critical values of the chi square distribution as visualized by **Table 5** are used in this publication.

Table 5. The critical values of the chi square distribution (degrees of freedom: 1)

	p-Value	One sided X²	Two sided X²
	0.1000000000	1.642374415	2.705543454
	0.0500000000	2.705543454	3.841458821
	0.0400000000	3.06490172	4.217884588
	0.0300000000	3.537384596	4.709292247
	0.0200000000	4.217884588	5.411894431
	0.0100000000	5.411894431	6.634896601
The chi square distribution	0.0010000000	9.549535706	10.82756617
	0.0001000000	13.83108362	15.13670523
	0.0000100000	18.18929348	19.51142096
	0.0000010000	22.59504266	23.92812698
	0.0000001000	27.03311129	28.37398736
	0.0000000100	31.49455797	32.84125335
	0.0000000010	35.97368894	37.32489311
	0.0000000001	40.46665791	41.82145620

3. Results

3.1 Without a Human Cytomegalovirus Infection no Glioblastoma Multiforme.

Claims.

Null hypothesis:

A cytomegalovirus infection is a necessary condition (a conditio sine qua non) of glioblastoma multiforme. In other words, the sample distribution of the study analyzed agrees with the hypothetical (theoretical) distribution of a necessary condition.

Alternative Hypothesis:

A cytomegalovirus infection is not a necessary condition (a conditio sine qua non) of glioblastoma multiforme. In other words, the sample distribution of the study analyzed does not agree with the hypothetical (theoretical) distribution of a necessary condition.

The significance level (Alpha) below which the null hypothesis will be rejected is alpha= 0.05.

Proof.

The results of the re-analyses of the data reviewed by this article (**Table 2**) which investigated the relationship between a cytomegalovirus infection and glioblastoma multiforme are viewed by the table (**Table 2**). Altogether, 16 studies were meta-analyzed while the level of significance was alpha = 0.05. In toto, 16 out of 16 studies provide significant evidence of a conditio sine qua non relationship between a cytomegalovirus infection and glioblastoma multiforme. The study of Dziurzynski et al. (2011) was significant according to the rule of three. *Some of the studies were performed without a control group which had no mathematical effect on the calculation of the chi square value of the conditio sine qua non relationship.* The most of the studies analyzed were able to provide evidence of a significant, positive cause effect relationship. In other words, the data analyzed support the Null-hypothesis: *without a cytomegalovirus infection no glioblastoma multiforme* (X² Calculated (SINE) = 16.19 and is less than X² Critical (SINE) = 24.996). **Q. e. d.**

3.2 HCMV is a Necessary and Sufficient Condition of Glioblastoma Multiforme

Null Hypothesis:

A cytomegalovirus infection is a necessary and sufficient condition of glioblastoma multiforme. In other words, the sample distribution of the study analyzed agrees with the hypothetical (theoretical) distribution of a necessary and sufficient condition.

Alternative Hypothesis:

A cytomegalovirus infection is not a *necessary and sufficient condition* of glioblastoma multiforme. In other words, the sample distribution of the study analyzed does not agree with the hypothetical (theoretical) distribution of a necessary and sufficient condition.

The significance level (Alpha) below which the null hypothesis will be rejected is $\alpha=0.05$.

Proof.

The results of the re-analyses of the data reviewed by this article (**Table 2**) which investigated the necessary and sufficient condition relationship between a cytomegalovirus infection and glioblastoma multiforme are viewed by the table (**Table 3**). Altogether, it was possible to consider 11 studies with a sample size of $N=718$ for a meta-analyzed while the level of significance was $\alpha = 0.05$. In toto, 11 out of 11 studies provide significant evidence (**Table 3**) of a necessary and sufficient conditions relationship (X^2 Calculated (SINE^{IMP}) = 8.3689 is less than X^2 Critical (SINE^{IMP}) = 16.918) while the causal relationship between a cytomegalovirus infection and glioblastoma multiforme was positive and significant. The studies of Dziurzynski et al. (Dziurzynski et al., 2011) and Stangherlin et al. (Stangherlin et al., 2016) were smaller than $N = 30$ and were analyzed according to the rule of three. Especially, the study of Rahbar et al. (Rahbar et al., 2012) detected HCMV-IEA in 79 (99%) of 80 GBM tumor cells *but not in surrounding non-tumor cells*. In general, a cytomegalovirus infection is a necessary and sufficient condition of glioblastoma multiforme (**Table 3**). **Q. e. d.**

3.3 HCMV is the Cause of Glioblastoma Multiforme

Several studies presented *missed an appropriate control groups* and were not considered for the analyses of the causal relationship between HCMV and GBM (**Table 2**).

Claims.

Null Hypothesis:

A cytomegalovirus infection is not the cause of glioblastoma multiforme. In other words. $k = 0$.

Alternative Hypothesis:

A cytomegalovirus infection is the cause of glioblastoma multiforme. In other words. $k \neq 0$.

The significance level (Alpha) below which the null hypothesis will be rejected is $\alpha=0.05$.

Proof.

The results of the re-analyses of the data reviewed by this article (**Table 2**) which investigated the causal relationship between a cytomegalovirus infection and glioblastoma multiforme are viewed by the table (**Table 3**). Altogether, 11 studies were meta-analyzed while the level of significance was $\alpha = 0.05$. In toto, 11 from 11 studies provided significant evidence of a causal relationship between a cytomegalovirus infection and glioblastoma multiforme. The studies of Dziurzynski et al. (2011) and Stangherlin et al. (Stangherlin et al., 2016) were smaller than $N = 30$. In the same respect, a cytomegalovirus infection is a necessary (**Table 2**) and a necessary and sufficient condition of glioblastoma multiforme (**Table 3**). In other words, *without* a HCMV infection *no* GBM. Thus far, the conclusion is inescapable. Human cytomegalovirus is the cause of glioblastoma multiforme ($k \sim 0.8608$, X^2 Calculated (k) = 532.06 and is greater than X^2 Critical (k) = 19.6751). **Q. e. d.**

4. Discussion

Due to the conflicting reports concerning the presence of the human cytomegalovirus in glioma tissue the association between human cytomegalovirus (HCMV) infection and glioblastoma is still a source of debate. While some studies detected HCMV DNA, RNA and proteins et cetera in GBM tissues others studies (Taha et al., 2016) have not. In most of the previous studies, only a very restricted number of HCMV viral targets with different sensitive techniques (Immunoglobulin G antibodies, immunohistochemical analysis, PCR, in situ hybridization, immunohistochemistry, real-time PCR et cetera) accompanied by a very different personal skill were analysed.

Thus, the question is justified to which extent was the (entire) viral genome detected at all when present. Furthermore, complicating issues are creating uncertainty about the results of the studies above which detected a strong relationship between HCMV with GBM tumours due to the relatively limited study population and non-randomization. In particular, sample quality (age or method of preservation) and primer selection has substantial effects on the outcome of a study. All these factors may have contributed to the few studies which were not able (Taha et al., 2016) to detect HCMV in GBMs tissues. In contrast to results like these, HCMV presence has been found in about 90-100% (Cobbs et al., 2002; Mitchell et al., 2008; Rahbar et al., 2012; Söderberg-Nauclér et al., 2013) of GBM tumors. Söderberg-Nauclér et al. (Söderberg-Nauclér et al., 2013) examined more than 250

cases of glioblastoma while only one of these patients was CMV-negative. Due to the missing control group, the very convincing data of the study of Söderberg-Nauclér et al. (2013) were not considered for causal analysis while the *conditio sine qua non* relationship is highly significant. Rahbar et al. (2012) detected HCMV infection in 79 of 80 patients (99%) GBM tumor samples. The surrounding non-tumor cells of the same patient served as the control group. Rahbar et al. (2012) were not able to detect HCMV in any of the controls i. e. HCMV was not detected in surrounding non-tumor cells. The results of the study of Rahbar et al. (2012) are viewed by **Table 6**. The single study of Rahbar et al. (2012) has provided striking evidence that HCMV infection is a necessary, a sufficient and a necessary and sufficient condition of GBM while the cause effect relationship between HCMV and GBM is highly significant. Thus far and ultimately, according to the study of Rahbar et al. (2012) HCMV is the cause of GBM and much more than this. The evidence of the studies presented cannot be ignored too. In point of fact, several studies did not present a suitable control group (**Table 2**). Thus far, it was not possible to consider these studies to calculate the causal relationship *k* between HCV and GBM. Besides of this limitation, the missed control group had no mathematical influence on the calculation of the chi square value of the necessary condition distribution. All but the study of Lucas et al. (2011) underdetermine empirically the Null-hypothesis: *without HCV no GBM*. In other words, GBM cannot develop without a HCV infection. It is obvious that the evidence of the relationship between HCV and GBM is much stronger than outlined just before. In toto, 11 studies with a sample size of *n*=718 (**Table 3**) support the Null-hypothesis that HCMV is a necessary and sufficient condition of GBM while the cause effect relationship *k* between HCMV and GBM is highly significant (**Table 3**). Ultimately, the evidence documented is extensive, solid and sufficient to justify the hypotheses that HCMV is the cause of GBM.

Table 6. The Study of Rahbar et al. (Rahbar et al., 2012)

		GBM 		
		Yes	No	Total
HCMV-IEA	Yes	79	0	79
<A>	No	1	80	81
Total		80	80	160

***k* =0.98757716**
p value (*k*) =8.258E-36
 WITHOUT <A> NO .
p (SINE) =0.99375
X²(SINE) =0.003125
 IF <A> THEN
p (IMP)=1
X² (IMP)=0.00316456
 <A> is SINE and IMP of
p(SINE ^ IMP) =0.99375
X²(SINE ^ IMP) =0.00628956

To date, aggressive treatment (Stupp et al., 2005) of glioblastoma multiforme with surgery, radiation therapy and chemotherapy are relatively ineffective due to the known aggressive nature of GBM and provides only a very limited overall survival benefit for these patients. In fact, there is no effective therapy or cure for glioblastoma multiforme while the life of the patients suffering from this disease is extremely (Smoll et al., 2013) endangered. New therapeutic strategies should be offered to counteract the poor prognosis of GBM. HCMV is the cause of GBM and has a major impact on morbidity, mortality and survival of GBM patients too. In this context, it is necessary to consider a highly effective and simple to practice anti-HCMV therapeutic strategy. HCMV appears to control the PGE 2 synthesis and the expression of COX-2 (Baryawno et al., 2011) in medulloblastomas. Valganciclovir and specific COX-2 inhibitors (Etoricoxib, Celecoxib) are able to prevent HCMV replication and to reduce medulloblastoma tumor cell growth in vitro and in vivo (Baryawno et al., 2011). Anti-CMV treatment has already reduced the growth of medulloblastoma by 72% in animal model (Baryawno et al., 2011). The double-blind Valcyte Treatment of Glioblastoma Patients in Sweden (VIGAS) clinical trial of valganciclovir (Söderberg-Nauclér et al., 2013) found that cases receiving at least 6 months of antiviral therapy had a significantly increased rate of 2-year survival (50% vs. 20.6%, *P*<0.001) compared with controls. In fact, an optimal treatment of CMV can help to improve the outcome of GBM patient and may focus additionally and primarily on ganciclovir or valganciclovir (Söderberg-Nauclér et al., 2013) and other similar drugs. In particular, drugs like etanercept, etoricoxib (Hung et al., 2017) and leflunomide (John et al., 2004; Suissa et al., 2006) are

simple to work with and are to some extent effective against human cytomegalovirus too. Ganciclovir, valganciclovir (Söderberg-Nauclér et al., 2013), etanercept, etoricoxib (Hung et al., 2017) and leflunomide (John et al., 2004; Suissa et al., 2006) is of strategic importance at least as an add-on therapy in patients suffering from glioblastoma multiforme. Thus far, it is useful to point out that John et al. (John et al., 2004) documented the efficacy of leflunomide in humans with CMV disease who received loading dose of 100 mg of leflunomide once daily on days 1–3 and then 20 mg once daily for three months. To date and for preliminary purposes, Etanercept, etoricoxib and leflunomide should become additionally one part of an effective intervention against glioblastoma multiforme. We see the bright colors and the beauty of galaxies so far away from our earth and listen very carefully to the heartbeat of deep space. I stubbornly refuse to accept the conclusions that we are unable to develop a low cost and highly effective vaccine (Inoue et al., 2018) against a CMV infection and even an appropriate DNA CMV therapeutic vaccine too. Historically this hope arises out of the experience that together we have achieved what divided was impossible. In addition, such an undertaking is an urgent and major public health duty too.

5. Conclusion

The studies presented in this publication provided a very impressive evidence of a cause effect relationship between HCMV and GBM. In any case, this publication invites us in an overwhelmingly plausible manner to leave aside any doubts and any uncertainty we might have about whether there is a cause effect relationship between HCMV and GBM. For a different view, until a contrary and more convincing experimental objections have been raised against the causal relationship between HCMV and GBM, according to this analysis it is necessary and justified to accept in agreement with the majority of studies presented that human cytomegalovirus is the cause of glioblastoma multiforme.

Acknowledgement

Dedicated to Celina.

References

- Altman, D. G. (1991). *Practical statistics for medical research* (1. ed.). London: Chapman and Hall. Retrieved from <http://www.loc.gov/catdir/enhancements/fy0646/91124890-d.html>
- Bailey, P., & Cushing, H. (1927). A classification of the tumours of the glioma group on a histogenetic basis, with a correlated study of prognosis. By Percival Bailey and Harvey Cushing. Medium 8vo. Pp. 175, with 108 illustrations. 1926. Philadelphia, London, and Montreal: J. B. Lippincott Company. 21s. net. *British Journal of Surgery*, 14, 554-555. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bjs.1800145540>
- Barukčić, I. (2016a). The Mathematical Formula of the Causal Relationship k. *International Journal of Applied Physics and Mathematics*, 6, 45-65. <https://doi.org/10.17706/ijapm.2016.6.2.45-65>
- Barukčić, J. P., & Barukčić, I. (2016b). Anti Aristotle—The Division of Zero by Zero. *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics*, 4, 749-761. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jamp.2016.44085>
- Barukčić, I. (2017a). Anti Bohr — Quantum Theory and Causality. *International Journal of Applied Physics and Mathematics*, 7, 93-111. <https://doi.org/10.17706/ijapm.2017.7.2.93-111>
- Barukčić, I. (2017b). *Die Kausalität*. Norderstedt: Books on Demand.
- Barukčić, I. (2017c). *Theoriae causalitatis principia mathematica*. Norderstedt: Books on Demand.
- Barukčić, I. (2018a). Epstein Bar Virus—The Cause of Hodgkin's Lymphoma. *Journal of Biosciences and Medicines*, 6, 75-100. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jbm.2018.61008>
- Barukčić, I. (2018b). Fusobacterium nucleatum—The Cause of Human Colorectal Cancer. *Journal of Biosciences and Medicines*, 6, 31-69. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jbm.2018.63004>
- Barukčić, I. (2018c). Human Papillomavirus—The Cause of Human Cervical Cancer. *Journal of Biosciences and Medicines*, 6, 106-125. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jbm.2018.64009>
- Barukčić, I. (2018d). Zero Divided by Zero Equals One. *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics*, 06, 836-853. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jamp.2018.64072>
- Barukčić, I. (2018e) Mycobacterium Avium Subspecies Paratuberculosis -The Cause of Crohn's Disease. *Modern Health Science*, 1, 19-34. <https://doi.org/10.30560/mhs.v1n1p19>
- Barukčić, I. (2018f) Helicobacter Pylori is the Cause of Gastric Cancer. *Modern Health Science*, 1, 43-50. <https://doi.org/10.30560/mhs.v1n1p43>
- Barukčić, I. (2018g) Gastric Cancer and Epstein-Barr Virus Infection. A Systematic Review of ISH Based

- Studies. *Modern Health Science*, 1, 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.30560/mhs.v1n2p1>
- Baryawno, N., Rahbar, A., Wolmer-Solberg, N., Taher, C., Odeberg, J., Darabi, A., Khan, Z., Sveinbjörnsson, B., Fuskevåg, O. M., Segerström, L., Nordenskjöld, M., Siesjö, P., Kogner, P., Johnsen, J. I., & Söderberg-Nauclér, C. (2011) Detection of human cytomegalovirus in medulloblastomas reveals a potential therapeutic target. *The Journal of Clinical Investigation*, 121, 4043-55. <https://doi.org/10.1172/JCI57147>
- Bhattacharjee, B., Renzette, N., & Kowalik, T. F. (2012). Genetic analysis of cytomegalovirus in malignant gliomas. *Journal of Virology*, 86, 6815-6824. <https://doi.org/10.1128/JVI.00015-12>
- Boeckh, M., Murphy, W. J., & Peggs, K. S. (2015). Recent advances in cytomegalovirus: an update on pharmacologic and cellular therapies. *Biology of Blood and Marrow Transplantation: Journal of the American Society for Blood and Marrow Transplantation*, 21, 24-29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbmt.2014.11.002>
- Bohr, N. (1937). Causality and Complementarity. *Philosophy of Science*, 4, 289-298. <https://doi.org/10.1086/286465>
- Bongartz, T., Sutton, A. J., Sweeting, M. J., Buchan, I., Matteson, E. L., & Montori, V. (2006). Anti-TNF antibody therapy in rheumatoid arthritis and the risk of serious infections and malignancies: systematic review and meta-analysis of rare harmful effects in randomized controlled trials. *JAMA*, 295, 2275-2285. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.295.19.2275>
- Cannon, M. J., Schmid, D. S., & Hyde, T. B. (2010). Review of cytomegalovirus seroprevalence and demographic characteristics associated with infection. *Reviews in Medical Virology*, 20, 202-213. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rmv.655>
- Choueiter, N. F., Olson, A. K., Shen, D. D., & Portman, M. A. (2010). Prospective open-label trial of etanercept as adjunctive therapy for kawasaki disease. *The Journal of Pediatrics*, 157, 960-966.e1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2010.06.014>
- Cimino, P. J., Zhao, G., Wang, D., Sehn, J. K., Lewis, J. S., & Duncavage, E. J. (2014). Detection of viral pathogens in high grade gliomas from unmapped next-generation sequencing data. *Experimental and Molecular Pathology*, 96, 310-315. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yexmp.2014.03.010>
- Cobbs, C. S., Harkins, L., Samanta, M., Gillespie, G. Y., Bharara, S., King, P. H., ... Britt, W. J. (2002). Human Cytomegalovirus Infection and Expression in Human Malignant Glioma. *Cancer Research*, 62(12), 3347-3350. Retrieved from <http://cancerres.aacrjournals.org/content/62/12/3347.full.pdf>
- Cornfield, J. (1951) A Method of Estimating Comparative Rates from Clinical Data. Applications to Cancer of the Lung, Breast, and Cervix. *JNCI: Journal of the National Cancer Institute*, 11, 1269-1275. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jnci/11.6.1269>
- Ding, D., Han, S., Wang, Z., Guo, Z., & Wu, A. (2014). Does the existence of HCMV components predict poor prognosis in glioma? *Journal of Neuro-Oncology*, 116, 515-522. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11060-013-1350-9>
- Dos Santos, C. J., Stangherlin, L. M., Figueiredo, E. G., Corrêa, C., Teixeira, M. J., & da Silva, M. C. C. (2014). High prevalence of HCMV and viral load in tumor tissues and peripheral blood of glioblastoma multiforme patients. *Journal of Medical Virology*, 86, 1953-1961. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmv.23820>
- Dziurzynski, K., Chang, S. M., Heimberger, A. B., Kalejta, R. F., McGregor Dallas, S. R., Smit, M., ... Cobbs, C. S. (2012). Consensus on the role of human cytomegalovirus in glioblastoma. *Neuro-Oncology*, 14, 246-255. <https://doi.org/10.1093/neuonc/nor227>
- Dziurzynski, K., Wei, J., Qiao, W., Hatiboglu, M. A., Kong, L. Y., Wu, A., ... Heimberger, A. B. (2011). Glioma-associated cytomegalovirus mediates subversion of the monocyte lineage to a tumor propagating phenotype. *Clinical Cancer Research: An Official Journal of the American Association for Cancer Research*, 17, 4642-4649. <https://doi.org/10.1158/1078-0432.CCR-11-0414>
- Edwards, A. W. F. (1963). The Measure of Association in a 2 × 2 Table. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series a (General)*, 126, 109-114. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2982448>
- Einstein, A. (1948). Quanten-Mechanik und Wirklichkeit. *Dialectica*, 2, 320-324. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1746-8361.1948.tb00704.x>
- Einstein, A., Podolsky, B., & Rosen, N. (1935). Can Quantum-Mechanical Description of Physical Reality Be Considered Complete? *Physical Review*, 47, 777-780. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRev.47.777>

- Fowler, K. B., Ross, S. A., Shimamura, M., Ahmed, A., Palmer, A. L., Michaels, M. G., ... Boppana, S. (2018). Racial and Ethnic Differences in the Prevalence of Congenital Cytomegalovirus Infection. *The Journal of Pediatrics*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2018.04.043>
- Gandhi, M. K., & Khanna, R. (2004). Human cytomegalovirus: Clinical aspects, immune regulation, and emerging treatments. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*, 4, 725-738. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(04\)01202-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(04)01202-2)
- Garcia-Martinez, A., Alenda, C., Irlles, E., Ochoa, E., Quintanar, T., Rodriguez-Lescure, A., ... Barbera, V. M. (2017). Lack of cytomegalovirus detection in human glioma. *Virology Journal*, 14, 216. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12985-017-0885-3>
- Gupta, D. K., Mahapatra, A., Sharma, M., & Kasliwal, M. (2007). Congenital glioblastoma multiforme: A case report and review of literature. *Journal of Pediatric Neurosciences*, 2, 69. <https://doi.org/10.4103/1817-1745.36766>
- Haerter, G., Manfras, B. J., Jong-Hesse, Y. de, Wilts, H., Mertens, T., Kern, P., & Schmitt, M. (2004). Cytomegalovirus retinitis in a patient treated with anti-tumor necrosis factor alpha antibody therapy for rheumatoid arthritis. *Clinical Infectious Diseases : an Official Publication of the Infectious Diseases Society of America*, 39, e88-94. <https://doi.org/10.1086/425123>
- Han, S., Wang, P. F., Xing, Y. X., Song, H. W., Yao, K., & Lin, Z. X. (2018). Human Cytomegalovirus (HCMV) infection was not correlated with overall survival in glioblastomas. *Neoplasma*, 65, 431-435. https://doi.org/10.4149/neo_2018_170124N59
- Hanley, J. A. (1983). If Nothing Goes Wrong, Is Everything All Right? *JAMA*, 249, 1743. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1983.03330370053031>
- Heisenberg, W. (1927). Über den anschaulichen Inhalt der quantentheoretischen Kinematik und Mechanik. *Zeitschrift Fr Physik*, 43, 172-198. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01397280>
- Holdhoff, M., Guner, G., Rodriguez, F. J., Hicks, J. L., Zheng, Q., Forman, M. S., ... Arav-Boger, R. (2017). Absence of Cytomegalovirus in Glioblastoma and Other High-grade Gliomas by Real-time PCR, Immunohistochemistry, and In Situ Hybridization. *Clinical Cancer Research: An Official Journal of the American Association for Cancer Research*, 23, 3150-3157. <https://doi.org/10.1158/1078-0432.CCR-16-1490>
- Holdhoff, M., Rothenberger, R., & Browner, I. E. (2018). Glioblastoma in older adults. *Aging*, 10, 154-155. <https://doi.org/10.18632/aging.101377>
- Hui-Yuen, J. S., Duong, T. T., & Yeung, R. S. M. (2006). TNF- Is Necessary for Induction of Coronary Artery Inflammation and Aneurysm Formation in an Animal Model of Kawasaki Disease. *The Journal of Immunology*, 176, 6294-6301. <https://doi.org/10.4049/jimmunol.176.10.6294>
- Hung, Y. M., Lin, L., Chen, C. M., Chiou, J. Y., Wang, Y. H., Wang, P. Y. P., & Wei, J. C. C. (2017). The effect of anti-rheumatic medications for coronary artery diseases risk in patients with rheumatoid arthritis might be changed over time: A nationwide population-based cohort study. *PloS One*, 12, e0179081. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0179081>
- John, G. T., Manivannan, J., Chandu, S., Peter, S., & Jacob, C. K. (2004). Leflunomide therapy for cytomegalovirus disease in renal allograft recipients. *Transplantation*, 77, 1460-1461. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.TP.0000122185.64004.89>
- Johnson, T. S., Abrams, Z. B., Mo, X., Zhang, Y., & Huang, K. (2017). Lack of human cytomegalovirus expression in single cells from glioblastoma tumors and cell lines. *Journal of Neurovirology*, 23, 671-678. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13365-017-0543-y>
- Jovanovic, B. D., & Levy, P. S. (1997). A Look at the Rule of Three. *The American Statistician*, 51, 137. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2685405>
- Kenneson, A., & Cannon, M. J. (2007). Review and meta-analysis of the epidemiology of congenital cytomegalovirus (CMV) infection. *Reviews in Medical Virology*, 17, 253-276. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rmv.535>
- Kolmogoroff, A. (1933). Grundbegriffe der Wahrscheinlichkeitsrechnung. Ergebnisse der Mathematik und Ihrer Grenzgebiete: Vol. 2. Berlin, Heidelberg, s.l.: Springer Berlin Heidelberg. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-49888-6>

- Landolfo, S., Gariglio, M., Gribaudo, G., & Lembo, D. (2003). The human cytomegalovirus. *Pharmacology & Therapeutics*, *98*, 269-297. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0163-7258\(03\)00034-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0163-7258(03)00034-2)
- Liao, T. L., Chen, Y. M., Liu, H. J., & Chen, D. Y. (2017). Risk and severity of herpes zoster in patients with rheumatoid arthritis receiving different immunosuppressive medications: a case-control study in Asia. *BMJ Open*, *7*, e014032. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2016-014032>
- Libard, S., Popova, S. N., Amini, R.-M., Kärjä, V., Pietiläinen, T., Hämäläinen, K. M., ... Alafuzoff, I. (2014). Human cytomegalovirus tegument protein pp65 is detected in all intra- and extra-axial brain tumours independent of the tumour type or grade. *PloS One*, *9*, e108861. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0108861>
- Louis, T. A. (1981). Confidence Intervals for a Binomial Parameter after Observing No Successes. *The American Statistician*, *35*, 154. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00031305.1981.10479337>
- Louis, D. N., Ohgaki, H., Wiestler, O. D., Cavenee, W. K., Burger, P. C., Jouvet, A., ... Kleihues, P. (2007). The 2007 WHO classification of tumours of the central nervous system. *Acta Neuropathologica*, *114*, 97-109. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00401-007-0243-4>
- Lu, C. H., Tsai, J. H., Wu, M. Z., Yu, C. L., & Hsieh, S. C. (2015). Can leflunomide play a role in cytomegalovirus disease prophylaxis besides its antirheumatic effects? *Antiviral Therapy*, *20*, 93-96. <https://doi.org/10.3851/IMP2796>
- Lucas, K. G., Bao, L., Bruggeman, R., Dunham, K., & Specht, C. (2011). The detection of CMV pp65 and IE1 in glioblastoma multiforme. *Journal of Neuro-Oncology*, *103*, 231-238. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11060-010-0383-6>
- Ludwig, A., & Hengel, H. (2009). Epidemiological impact and disease burden of congenital cytomegalovirus infection in Europe. *Euro Surveillance: Bulletin Europeen Sur Les Maladies Transmissibles = European Communicable Disease Bulletin*, *14*, 26-32. <https://doi.org/10.2807/ese.14.09.19140-en>
- McFaline-Figueroa, J. R., & Wen, P. Y. (2017). The Viral Connection to Glioblastoma. *Current Infectious Disease Reports*, *19*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11908-017-0563-z>
- Mitchell, D. A., Xie, W., Schmittling, R., Learn, C., Friedman, A., McLendon, R. E., & Sampson, J. H. (2008). Sensitive detection of human cytomegalovirus in tumors and peripheral blood of patients diagnosed with glioblastoma. *Neuro-Oncology*, *10*, 10-18. <https://doi.org/10.1215/15228517-2007-035>
- Mosteller, F. (1968). Association and Estimation in Contingency Tables. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, *63*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2283825>
- Nagasawa, D. T., Chow, F., Yew, A., Kim, W., Cremer, N., & Yang, I. (2012). Temozolomide and Other Potential Agents for the Treatment of Glioblastoma Multiforme. *Neurosurgery Clinics of North America*, *23*, 307-322. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nec.2012.01.007>
- Najafi, S., Ghane, M., Poortahmasebi, V., Jazayeri, S. M., & Yousefzadeh-Chabok, S. (2016). Prevalence of Cytomegalovirus in Patients With Multiple Sclerosis: A Case-Control Study in Northern Iran. *Jundishapur Journal of Microbiology*, *9*, e36582. <https://doi.org/10.5812/jjm.36582>
- Ohgaki, H. (2009). Epidemiology of brain tumors. *Methods in Molecular Biology (Clifton, N.J.)*, *472*, 323-342. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-60327-492-0_14
- Olsson, J., Kok, E., Adolfsson, R., Lövhelm, H., & Elgh, F. (2017). Herpes virus seroepidemiology in the adult Swedish population. *Immunity & Ageing: I & a*, *14*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12979-017-0093-4>
- Pagano, M., & Gauvreau, K. (2018). Principles of Biostatistics, Second Edition (2nd ed.). Milton: CRC Press. Retrieved from <https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/gbv/detail.action?docID=5301930>
- Pearson, K. (1896). Mathematical Contributions to the Theory of Evolution. III. Regression, Heredity, and Panmixia. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society a: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, *187*, 253-318. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.1896.0007>
- Pearson, K. (1900). X. On the criterion that a given system of deviations from the probable in the case of a correlated system of variables is such that it can be reasonably supposed to have arisen from random sampling. *The London, Edinburgh, and Dublin Philosophical Magazine and Journal of Science*, *50*, 157-175. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14786440009463897>
- Pearson, K. (1904). On the theory of contingency and its relation to association and normal correlation. London,

- 1-46. Retrieved from <https://archive.org/details/cu31924003064833>
- Petersen, B., & Lorentzen, H. (2008). Cytomegalovirus complicating biological immunosuppressive therapy in two patients with psoriasis receiving treatment with etanercept or efalizumab. *Acta Dermato-Venereologica*, 88, 523-524. <https://doi.org/10.2340/00015555-0491>
- Poltermann, S., Schlehofer, B., Steindorf, K., Schnitzler, P., Geletneky, K., & Schlehofer, J. R. (2006). Lack of association of herpesviruses with brain tumors. *Journal of Neurovirology*, 12, 90-99. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13550280600654573>
- Prasad, V., Rajesh, A., Purohit, A., & Uppin, M. (2017). A rare case of congenital glioblastoma with atypical presentation in an eleven month-old infant: Case report with review of literature. *Asian Journal of Neurosurgery*, 12, 72. <https://doi.org/10.4103/1793-5482.145103>
- Priel, E., Wohl, A., Teperberg, M., Nass, D., & Cohen, Z. R. (2015). Human cytomegalovirus viral load in tumor and peripheral blood samples of patients with malignant gliomas. *Journal of Clinical Neuroscience: Official Journal of the Neurosurgical Society of Australasia*, 22, 326-330. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocn.2014.06.099>
- Rahbar, A., Stragliotto, G., Orrego, A., Peredo, I., Taher, C., Willems, J., & Söderberg-Naucler, C. (2012) Low levels of Human Cytomegalovirus Infection in Glioblastoma multiforme associates with patient survival; -a case-control study. *Herpesviridae*, 3(3). <https://doi.org/10.1186/2042-4280-3-3>
- Rahbar, A., Orrego, A., Peredo, I., Dzabic, M., Wolmer-Solberg, N., Strååt, K., ... Söderberg-Nauclér, C. (2013) Human cytomegalovirus infection levels in glioblastoma multiforme are of prognostic value for survival. *Journal of Clinical Virology: The Official Publication of the Pan American Society for Clinical Virology*, 57, 36-42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcv.2012.12.018>
- Ranganathan, P., Clark, P. A., Kuo, J. S., Salamat, M. S., & Kalejta, R. F. (2012). Significant association of multiple human cytomegalovirus genomic Loci with glioblastoma multiforme samples. *Journal of Virology*, 86, 854-864. <https://doi.org/10.1128/JVI.06097-11>
- Rumke, C. L. (1975). Implications of the Statement: No Side Effects Were Observed. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 292, 372-373. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM197502132920723>
- Scheurer, M. E., Bondy, M. L., Aldape, K. D., Albrecht, T., & El-Zein, R. (2008). Detection of human cytomegalovirus in different histological types of gliomas. *Acta Neuropathologica*, 116, 79-86. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00401-008-0359-1>
- Schleiss, M. R. (2013). Cytomegalovirus in the neonate: immune correlates of infection and protection. *Clinical & Developmental Immunology*, 2013, 501801. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/501801>
- Sinclair, J., & Reeves, M. (2014). The intimate relationship between human cytomegalovirus and the dendritic cell lineage. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 5, 595. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2014.00389>
- Slinger, E., Maussang, D., Schreiber, A., Siderius, M., Rahbar, A., Fraile-Ramos, A., ... Smit, M. J. (2010). HCMV-encoded chemokine receptor US28 mediates proliferative signaling through the IL-6-STAT3 axis. *Science Signaling*, 3, ra58. <https://doi.org/10.1126/scisignal.2001180>
- Smoll, N. R., Schaller, K., & Gautschi, O. P. (2013). Long-term survival of patients with glioblastoma multiforme (GBM). *Journal of Clinical Neuroscience: Official Journal of the Neurosurgical Society of Australasia*, 20, 670-675. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocn.2012.05.040>
- Sober, E. (2001). Venetian Sea Levels, British Bread Prices, and the Principle of the Common Cause. *The British Journal for the Philosophy of Science*, 52, 331-346. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjps/52.2.331>
- Söderberg-Nauclér, C., Rahbar, A., & Stragliotto, G. (2013) Survival in patients with glioblastoma receiving valganciclovir. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 369, 985-986. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMc1302145>
- Söderberg-Nauclér, C. (2015) Cytomegalovirus in human brain tumors: Role in pathogenesis and potential treatment options. *World Journal of Experimental Medicine*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.5493/wjem.v5.i1.1>
- Solomon, I. H., Ramkissoon, S. H., Milner, D. A., & Folkert, R. D. (2014). Cytomegalovirus and glioblastoma: a review of evidence for their association and indications for testing and treatment. *Journal of Neuropathology and Experimental Neurology*, 73, 994-998. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NEN.0000000000000125>
- Strååt, K., Liu, C., Rahbar, A., Zhu, Q., Liu, L., Wolmer-Solberg, N., ... Xu, D. (2009). Activation of telomerase

- by human cytomegalovirus. *Journal of the National Cancer Institute*, 101, 488-497. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jnci/djp031>
- Stragliotto, G., Rahbar, A., Solberg, N. W., Lilja, A., Taher, C., Orrego, A., ... Söderberg-Nauclér, C. (2013). Effects of valganciclovir as an add-on therapy in patients with cytomegalovirus-positive glioblastoma: A randomized, double-blind, hypothesis-generating study. *International Journal of Cancer*, 133, 1204-1213. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijc.28111>
- Stupp, R., Mason, W. P., van den Bent, M. J., Weller, M., Fisher, B., Taphoorn, M. J. B., ... Mirimanoff, R. O. (2005). Radiotherapy plus concomitant and adjuvant temozolomide for glioblastoma. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 352, 987-996. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa043330>
- Sudarsanam, T. D., Sahni, R. D., & John, G. T. (2006). Leflunomide: A possible alternative for ganciclovir sensitive and resistant cytomegalovirus infections. *Postgraduate Medical Journal*, 82, 313-314. <https://doi.org/10.1136/pgmj.2005.038521>
- Suissa, S., Bernatsky, S., & Hudson, M. (2006). Antirheumatic drug use and the risk of acute myocardial infarction. *Arthritis and Rheumatism*, 55, 531-536. <https://doi.org/10.1002/art.22094>
- Taha, M. S., Abdalhamid, B. A., El-Badawy, S. A., Sorour, Y. M., Almsned, F. M., & Al-Abbadi, M. A. (2016). Expression of cytomegalovirus in glioblastoma multiforme: Myth or reality? *British Journal of Neurosurgery*, 30, 307-312. <https://doi.org/10.3109/02688697.2015.1119241>
- Urbańska, K., Sokołowska, J., Szmidi, M., & Sysa, P. (2014). Review Glioblastoma multiforme – an overview. *Współczesna Onkologia*, 5, 307-312. <https://doi.org/10.5114/wo.2014.40559>
- Verhaak, R. G. W., Hoadley, K. A., Purdom, E., Wang, V., Qi, Y., Wilkerson, M. D., ... Hayes, D. N. (2010). Integrated genomic analysis identifies clinically relevant subtypes of glioblastoma characterized by abnormalities in PDGFRA, IDH1, EGFR, and NF1. *Cancer Cell*, 17, 98-110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccr.2009.12.020>
- Verkaik, N. J., Hoek, R. A. S., van Bergeijk, H., van Hal, P. T. W., Schipper, M. E. I., Pas, S. D., ... Murk, J. L. (2013). Leflunomide as part of the treatment for multidrug-resistant cytomegalovirus disease after lung transplantation: case report and review of the literature. *Transplant Infectious Disease: An Official Journal of the Transplantation Society*, 15, E243-9. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tid.12156>
- Waldman, W. J., Knight, D. A., Blinder, L., Shen, J., Lurain, N. S., Miller, D. M., ... Chong, A. S. (1999). Inhibition of cytomegalovirus in vitro and in vivo by the experimental immunosuppressive agent leflunomide. *Intervirology*, 42, 412-418. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000053979>
- Wang, C., Zhang, X., Bialek, S., & Cannon, M. J. (2011). Attribution of congenital cytomegalovirus infection to primary versus non-primary maternal infection. *Clinical Infectious Diseases: An Official Publication of the Infectious Diseases Society of America*, 52, e11-3. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciq085>
- Warrens, M. J. (2008). On Association Coefficients for 2x2 Tables and Properties That Do Not Depend on the Marginal Distributions. *Psychometrika*, 73, 777-789. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11336-008-9070-3>
- Weller, M., van den Bent, M., Tonn, J. C., Stupp, R., Preusser, M., Cohen-Jonathan-Moyal, E., ... Wick, W. (2017). European Association for Neuro-Oncology (EANO) guideline on the diagnosis and treatment of adult astrocytic and oligodendroglial gliomas. *The Lancet Oncology*, 18, e315-e329. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045\(17\)30194-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045(17)30194-8)
- Wensch, M., Weinberg, A., Wiencke, J., Miike, R., Sison, J., Wiemels, J., ... Kelsey, K. (2005). History of chickenpox and shingles and prevalence of antibodies to varicella-zoster virus and three other herpesviruses among adults with glioma and controls. *American Journal of Epidemiology*, 161, 929-938. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aje/kwi119>
- Wright, S. (1921). Correlation and Causation. *Journal of Agricultural Research*, 20, 557-585.
- Xing, Y., Wang, Y., Wang, S., Wang, X., Fan, D., Zhou, D., & An, J. (2016). Human cytomegalovirus infection contributes to glioma disease progression via upregulating endocan expression. *Translational Research: the Journal of Laboratory and Clinical Medicine*, 177, 113-126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trsl.2016.06.008>
- Yamane, T. (Ed.) (1964). *Statistics. An introductory analysis: Harper International Edition.*
- Yamashita, Y., Ito, Y., Isomura, H., Takemura, N., Okamoto, A., Motomura, K., ... Tsurumi, T. (2014). Lack of presence of the human cytomegalovirus in human glioblastoma. *Modern Pathology: An Official Journal of the United States and Canadian Academy of Pathology, Inc*, 27, 922-929.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/modpathol.2013.219>

- Yang, C. F., Ho, H. L., Lin, S. C., Hsu, C. Y., & Ho, D. M. T. (2017). Detection of human cytomegalovirus in glioblastoma among Taiwanese subjects. *PloS One*, *12*, e0179366. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0179366>
- Yates, F. (1934). Contingency Tables Involving Small Numbers and the X^2 Test. *The Journal of the Royal Statistical Society (Supplement)*, *1*, 217-235. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2983604>
- Yi, F., Zhao, J., Luckheeram, R. V., Lei, Y., Wang, C., Huang, S., ... Xia, B. (2013). The prevalence and risk factors of cytomegalovirus infection in inflammatory bowel disease in Wuhan, Central China. *Virology Journal*, *10*(43). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1743-422X-10-43>
- Yuan, X., Curtin, J., Xiong, Y., Liu, G., Waschmann-Hogiu, S., Farkas, D. L., ... Yu, J. S. (2004). Isolation of cancer stem cells from adult glioblastoma multiforme. *Oncogene*, *23*, 9392-9400. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.onc.1208311>
- Yule, G. U. (1900). On the Association of Attributes in Statistics: With Illustrations from the Material of the Childhood Society, &c. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society a: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, *194*, 257-319. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.1900.0019>
- Zavala-Vega, S., Castro-Escarpulli, G., Hernández-Santos, H., Salinas-Lara, C., Palma, I., Mejía-Aranguré, J. M., ... Arellano-Galindo, J. (2017). An overview of the infection of CMV, HSV 1/2 and EBV in Mexican patients with glioblastoma multiforme. *Pathology, Research and Practice*, *213*, 271-276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prp.2016.12.006>
- Zhu, Y., & Parada, L. F. (2002). The molecular and genetic basis of neurological tumours. *Nature Reviews. Cancer*, *2*, 616-626. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrc866>

Copyrights

Copyright for this article is retained by the author(s), with first publication rights granted to the journal.

This is an open-access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).